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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XVI
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This note is a first attempt to specify the output from the DS-reductions with reference to the format for the final Hipparcos Catalogue.

1. Introduction

One major difficulty in the DS-processing is the large number of different 'categories' of double and multiple systems that have to be treated differently. Although the *majority* of non-singles will be physical binaries, with linearly moving, non-variable components, there are thousands of more complicated systems already in the Input Catalogue, and several more to be discovered. This is a problem in the reductions, and it will be a problem when the data are going to be published. I have as yet too limited experience with the solutions to be able to list all complications, but the following discussion raises some important points.

2. Simple cases

For a great majority of doubles, both known and newly discovered, a 12-parameter solution is sufficient. Both STDDBL and SEEKDBL give as raw output the magnitude, positions, proper motions and parallax for the primary and for the secondary relative to the primary. There is often an advantage, however, to constrain the solution to give equal parallaxes for the two components ('physical double') or even to neglect all internal motions ('fixed secondary'). In NDAC, these three different solutions are routinely obtained, and the complete solution (including covariances) is thus specified by $12+144+11+121+9+81=378$ numbers. This can (and should!) be given in machine-readable form, to enable a subsequent computation of any relevant combination of parameters (with their mean errors). In a printed version of the data, the most useful such combinations should be presented. Because the data may be used in a variety of ways, I think a minimum output is as follows.

A first part of the output-table could contain 'absolute' astrometric data (for a fixed standard epoch around 1992.0). Here the position, parallax and proper motion for the primary, the photocentre and the secondary would be listed (together with their mean errors). An automatic procedure could ensure that the solution with individual parallaxes is used when they differ by more than some 3σ , otherwise the common parallax solution. The photocentre position could e.g. be given for all separations below 3 arcsec, but noting that the effective wavelength for the Hipparcos observations differs significantly from standard photographic ones. For the closest separations (below 0.2 arcsec), the photocentre position is better known than the positions of the individual components. For physical doubles, an interesting datum is of course the position and proper motion for the barycentre, and this may be easily calculated from the pr/sec-data once a mass-ratio is assumed.

Comp	α	δ	μ_α	μ_δ	π
pr	2 8 55.72483(13)	70 31 36.3472(18)	-.0094(15)	-.0028(13)	.0053(12)
pc	2 8 55.73476(15)	70 31 36.4298(20)	-.0090(18)	-.0030(17)	.0053(12)
sec	2 8 55.76063(43)	70 31 36.6481(59)	-.0081(42)	-.0034(42)	.0053(12)

Then the relative astrometric data (sec-pr) may be given in a second part of the table. The first line gives the full solution, with a possible parallax-difference between the components (label 'opt'). The second line is a standard solution for a physical double (constrained to zero relative parallax), and the third line gives the 'fixed secondary' solution. The sep/PA-entries are given only for convenience when comparing with other data. The full accuracy is retained only in the rectangular x/y and their time derivatives $\dot{x}, \dot{y}$. (To save place, the 'opt' entry would probably only be given when $\Delta\pi$ is significantly non-zero).

Case	sep	PA	x	y	$\dot{x}$	$\dot{y}$	$\Delta\pi$
opt	0.34	28.0	0.1602(36)	0.3009(42)	0.0015(38)	-0.0021(42)	0.0025(42)
phys	0.34	28.2	0.1612(34)	0.3011(32)	0.0013(26)	-0.0006(30)	0.0000(00)
fix	0.34	28.6	0.1630(22)	0.2992(21)	0.0000(00)	0.0000(00)	0.0000(00)

Finally, the photometric data would have to be given. For wider doubles, individual colours are available from the star-mapper or from ground-based observations, but for a majority of close doubles, only a mean colour is available. (The resulting systematic errors in the astrometry will be insignificant, but for the photometry, the effects have to be studied carefully). Except for the colours, the photometric output is the H_p -magnitudes for the two components, their difference (Δm), and for closer pairs the total (pc) magnitude. The Δm :s in particular are an important product of the Hipparcos observations that will vastly improve our knowledge of the mass-ratio distributions for physical binaries.

A problem exists also to label correctly the 'new' discoveries. The Input Catalogue lacks many close pairs discovered e.g. by speckle interferometry. Some of these have been added by the DRC from other catalogues and lists, but several pairs already observed from the ground will be 'discovered' by Hipparcos. An effort has to be made to cross-correlate the data with more complete catalogues (in particular the WDS) before publication.

3. Moving doubles

The above output is mostly sufficient, but the 'problem cases' are actually the most interesting ones. First, the relative motion in a short-period binary may be definitely non-linear. The standard output for such 'moving' binaries could consist of a number (3-5) of individual positions derived from 9-12 months of observations. A problem is that *both* the absolute and the relative positions would change, making for a rather messy and big output. It may be better to make two extreme assumptions about the mass-ratio (probably bracketing the true one), and to give the data for the barycentre in the above format.

q	α	δ	μ_α	μ_δ	π
0.3	2 8 55.73309(13)	70 31 36.4166(15)	-.0091(16)	-.0029(17)	.0053(12)
0.7	2 8 55.73957(13)	70 31 36.4711(15)	-.0089(16)	-.0030(17)	.0053(12)

Then the individual relative positions could be given with their mean epochs

epoch	sep	PA	x	y
1990.42	0.35	30.7	0.179(08)	0.301(09)
1991.28	0.31	42.7	0.212(09)	0.228(09)
1992.12	0.25	50.3	0.196(10)	0.166(11)
1993.22	0.23	58.4	0.194(10)	0.120(10)
1993.97	0.18	80.7	0.178(10)	0.030(10)

For very rapidly moving systems and/or systems where a preliminary orbit is known from earlier observations, it may be possible to improve the orbit using the Hipparcos data. Such processing has to be done with different assumptions for each individual system, and should probably not be part of the general reductions. The data could be made available as 'semi-reduced' observations (like NDAC's Case History Files). Such data may be very valuable when used in conjunction with later ground-based studies, and it is important that they are preserved (together with sufficient instructions for their use).

The 'astrometric' doubles are related to the above moving systems, but here only the primary or the photocentre is observed. (If this motion is linear, the system is indistinguishable from a single star). If the orbital period is above some ten years, a set of individual 'absolute' positions may be obtained, but in most cases, an approximate orbit will already be known. One may then adjust some parameter(s) of the orbit, but again the treatment will be different for individual systems.

4. Variable components

Above it was implicitly assumed that the individual component stars are photometrically constant. At least several hundred doubles show variations in light that have to be taken into account. In many cases, it may be possible to derive a common astrometric solution but with individual magnitude-determinations at each observation epoch. If the variations are periodic, a light-curve may be derived together with a good astrometric solution. In most other cases, one of the components is constant, and individual magnitudes for the other may be given. Again, the many possible combinations of astrometric and photometric 'difficulty' makes it hard to be more specific.

5. Multiple stars

Some 500 multiples are known in the Input Catalogue, but probably rather many new triples will be discovered among the known doubles. Indeed, most of the multiples are hierarchical triples, with a 'close' and a 'wide' pair with greatly differing separations. For them, the above output-formats may be used unchanged for the close pair, and the only addition needed is an extra entry in the 'absolute' part with the position of the 'single' component. (In a few cases, even the wide separation is below 3 arcsec, and then a single photocentre for all three objects may be given).

For the non-hierarchical 'trapezium'-multiples, absolute (and relative?) positions have to be given for all objects, generally assuming a common parallax. (Additional complications may occur, like the *two* eclipsing binaries in the Orion Trapezium...).

6. Conclusions

The Hipparcos data for doubles and multiples are rich and varied, but therefore also difficult to publish in a uniform way. The data reductions have to be made with the publication in mind, and several versions of 'sample'-output may have to be tested. Even the 'simple' output above probably takes 4 lines per system over two printed pages, some 1000 pages for 12500 systems. With moving, variable and multiple systems included, a multi-volume catalogue can be anticipated.

With their very different reduction-methods, it is also unlikely that FAST and NDAC will find data that may be meaningfully combined for more than some (major?) part of the non-singles. The reliability of the different solutions has to be tested as well as possible by comparisons with ground-based data, but e.g. Δm -values are simply not available. Maybe the data from both consortia should be published in conflicting cases, as an indication of the uncertainty of interpretation. It is important, however, that in these and other complicated cases, the basic 'semi-reduced' data is made available in some form (CHF:s?). With supplementary ground-based observations, these data may later prove very useful to double-star astronomy.